

MEO: An Enhanced MEC Orchestrator for Federated and Distributed MEC Systems

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Abstract—Resource distribution among diverse administrative domains, network operators, and geographical locations across the edge-to-cloud continuum requires suitable communication and management and orchestration (MANO) mechanisms among orchestration domains. In multi-access edge computing (MEC) environments, efficient application lifecycle management and system federation are essential for scalability, optimal resource utilization, and ensuring service continuity and reliability. Existing orchestration solutions, typically designed for centralized cloud architectures, often fall short in accommodating application delay requirements and in managing the dynamic and distributed nature of MEC resources effectively. This paper introduces a cloud-native, platform-agnostic MEC Orchestrator (MEO) with enhancements over the ETSI MEC architecture, albeit aligned with GSMA and ETSI MEC federation standards, that supports cross-platform MANO and resource controllability. Federation is supported through a new MEO-to-MEO interface that enables application migration across MEC systems. Experimental results demonstrate a 95% instantiation success rate for instantiation, overperforming the baseline Kubernetes scheduler, and 93.3% for migration requests within federated MEC systems in high request volume scenarios.

Index Terms—MEC, 6G, Orchestration, Network Management, Federation, Cloud-Native.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of fifth generation (5G) cellular systems emphasizes the need for both low-latency and high-bandwidth communications, positioning multi-access edge computing (MEC) as a key enabler for the provisioning of novel use cases. MEC revolutionizes the traditional network architecture by decentralizing computing resources to the edge, facilitating localized data processing and content delivery, thus enabling use cases that require processing capabilities next to the end users. Standardization bodies such as GSMA [1] and ETSI [2] play a crucial role in defining the framework for MEC, focusing on interoperability, scalability, and efficiency.

Recently, the concept of MEC federation has emerged as an enabler for the collaboration of MECs across multiple infrastructure owners. MEC federation refers to the interconnection of MEC systems to ensure the consistent delivery of services and applications across different infrastructure domains, introducing new capabilities such as the ability for verticals to choose the

optimal MEC for application instantiation [3]. However, as network resources become dispersed across diverse geographical locations and are managed by various MEC orchestrators, the task of coordinating access to these distributed resources grows increasingly complex. This complexity is particularly evident in the management and orchestration (MANO) of systems that span multiple domains and incorporate a vast array of resources. In this regard, effective mechanisms for application lifecycle management are needed, to guarantee both the efficient usage of computational resources and application requirements. Open-source solutions such as Open Source MANO (OSM) [4], Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP) [5], Open Baton [6], and X-MANO [7], have emerged to enhance the MANO of virtualized environments. While these solutions significantly improve operational efficiency, their design largely focuses on centralized cloud architectures, and they don't meet the needs of federated and distributed MEC environments. Conversely, the SONATA framework [8] emerged as a significant advancement in distributed MANO solutions for 5G, with a modular architecture that enables the flexible integration of orchestration mechanisms. In addition, [9] explored automated orchestration across multiple domains to streamline the deployment of network services. However, the solutions in [8] and [9] perform poorly in terms of scalability and service instantiation time.

On the other hand, the establishment of MEC federation across infrastructure owners requires MEC-to-MEC communication mechanisms. The work in [10] proposed the utilization of direct interfaces among MEC platforms, leading to challenges in service deployment and limited scalability. Moreover, [11] explored a multi-mobile network operator MEC federation proof of concept, using East/West-bound interfaces to link multiple MNO MEC systems. Further, [12] discussed the deployment of services across distributed resources at the edge of the network, enabling low-latency access for verticals. However, the aforementioned works did not provide a standardized framework for infrastructure owners to expose system capabilities, hindering cross-platform interoperability.

To address the shortcomings in the literature, this paper introduces a MEC Orchestrator (MEO) tailored to distributed, multi-domain environments. Its design adheres to GSMA [13] [14]

across all the MEC hosts located within the virtual infrastructure manager (VIM), according to application requirements and incoming deployment requests. The onboarding and updating of application descriptors are managed through a dedicated database. Additionally, the MEO utilizes customized capability exporters to gather information on infrastructure resources, performance metrics, and the status of MEC applications.

Moreover, the MEO includes a federation module to handle the interconnection with MEC systems, following GSMA [14] and ETSI MEC federation [15] standards. This connection is employed to facilitate the exchange of information concerning infrastructure and computational capabilities, and the utilization of resources across different domains, in an interoperable manner. Moreover, the MEO-to-MEO interface supports the migration of MEC applications between different MEC systems when application requirements are no longer met, thus increasing fault tolerance. A northbound API is the entry point to the MEO from the Operations Support System (OSS) [16]. A southbound REST API connects the MEO to the MECPM, which performs necessary operations on the VIM. Related functionalities and workflows are provided in Section II-E.

D. MEC host selection mechanism

Below, a scheduling mechanism is proposed for the selection of MEC hosts for application deployment in distributed MEC systems.

Let $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ denote the set of nodes within the MEC system. For every node n in \mathcal{N} , available resources are defined in terms of CPU (γ), RAM (ρ), storage (σ), and delay (δ) resources for any given state s in the set of possible states $\mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, S\}$. The resource availability vector for host n at state s is expressed as $\mathbf{A}_n^s = [A^{\gamma_n^s}, A^{\rho_n^s}, A^{\sigma_n^s}, A^{\delta_n^s}]$. Vector \mathbf{A} is dynamically updated whenever a new application is deployed within the MEC system. For node n , the allocatable capacity limits for CPU, RAM, and storage are given by the vector $\mathbf{C}_n = [\gamma_n^{\max}, \rho_n^{\max}, \sigma_n^{\max}]$.

Moreover, let $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, K\}$ represent the set of application instantiation requests. Each application request $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is defined by a request vector \mathbf{R}_k , which specifies the required computational resources (CPU, RAM, and storage) along with the maximum allowable delay budget for the application, formulated as $\mathbf{R}_k = [R_k^\gamma, R_k^\rho, R_k^\sigma, R_k^\delta]$. The system model parameters are summarized in Table I.

To mathematically model the MEC host selection problem, two binary variables are introduced: x_n represents the operational status of node n , and y_n^k , indicates if request $k \in \mathcal{K}$ has been successfully allocated and initiated on node n , i.e.:

$$x_n = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if node } n \text{ is active,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$y_n^k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if request } k \text{ is successfully deployed in node } n, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The problem at hand involves the maximization of the number of application requests that are successfully deployed:

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE SYSTEM MODEL PARAMETERS.

Notation	Description
\mathcal{N}	Number of nodes in each MEC system, $n \in [1, \mathcal{N}]$
\mathcal{S}	States of the network, $s \in \mathcal{S}$
\mathbf{A}_n^s	Resource availability vector for any state $s \in \mathcal{S}$ at node $n \in \mathcal{N}$ $\mathbf{A}_n^s = [A^{\gamma_n^s}, A^{\rho_n^s}, A^{\sigma_n^s}, A^{\delta_n^s}]$
\mathbf{C}_n	Maximum capacity vector for computational resources at each MEC host $n \in \mathcal{N}$ $\mathbf{C}_n = [\gamma_n^{\max}, \rho_n^{\max}, \sigma_n^{\max}]$
\mathcal{K}	Set of application instantiation requests, $k \in [1, \mathcal{K}]$
\mathbf{R}_k	Request vector detailing computational resources and maximum allowable delay $\mathbf{R}_k = [R_k^\gamma, R_k^\rho, R_k^\sigma, R_k^\delta]$

$$\max \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} y_n^k \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} R_k^{\{\gamma, \rho, \sigma\}} \leq A^{\{\gamma, \rho, \sigma\}_n^s} \cdot x_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} y_n^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (3c)$$

$$R_k^\delta \leq A^{\delta_n^s} \cdot y_n^k \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3d)$$

$$x_n = 1 \Rightarrow y_n^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (3e)$$

Constraint (3b) ensures that the sum of the computational resources demanded by all requests allocated on any node $n \in \mathcal{N}$ must not surpass its total capacity in terms of CPU (γ), RAM (ρ), or storage (σ) resources. Constraint (3c) ensures that each request k can be allocated to at most one node n . Constraint (3d) dictates that the delay δ must not exceed the designated maximum for a given request k , R_k^δ , thereby maintaining acceptable application performance. Additionally, constraint (3e) guarantees that an application can only be allocated to an active node.

Algorithm 1 MEC Host Selection Mechanism

Initialization:

Sort \mathcal{K} in descending order of resource and delay requirements.

Sort \mathcal{N} in descending order of total available resources.

Resource Matching and Allocation:

while \mathcal{K} is not empty **do**

for each application request $k \in \mathcal{K}$ **do**

for each MEC node $n \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**

if Constraints (3b), (3d) and (3e) hold

then

 Allocate k to n , set $y_n^k = 1$.

 Update \mathbf{A}_n^s .

end if

end for

end for

end while

Output: Set of allocation results $[y_n^1 \cdots y_n^K]$.

To address the problem given in Eq. (3a), a lightweight scheduling mechanism based on a sorting algorithm is proposed,

as detailed in Algorithm 1. The performance of this algorithm is evaluated in Section III. Moreover, the computational complexity of Algorithm 1 is given by $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{N} \cdot \mathcal{K})$. In the worst case, one iteration is required per each application request \mathcal{K} , and per each MEC node \mathcal{N} .

E. Functionalities and Workflow

The MEO's support functions encompass managing system telemetry, monitoring node states, and facilitating orchestrator communication. It oversees the lifecycle of MEC applications, responding to alarms signaling resource anomalies or operational inconsistencies to preempt failures and reduce downtime. An essential feature is the application registry, which compiles a comprehensive database of all applications, enhancing system organization and access. The MEO provides high service deployment flexibility, allowing instantiation at both near-edges and far-edges based on specific criteria, including location-specific requirements detailed in application descriptors. Moreover, application migration enables the smooth transition of applications either within the same MEC system or to a different one, through the MEO-to-MEO interface. The application migration process can be triggered dynamically by an internal alarm, when application requirements are no longer met, or by the OSS. This ensures that applications are efficiently relocated to a MEC host that fulfills their computational requirements and delay constraints, responding to changing conditions, and thereby enhancing operational efficiency and resource utilization.

MEC application onboarding is initiated from the OSS through the MEO's entry point. There are two distinct approaches to the application onboarding process. In the first approach, the deployer entity could pre-onboard an application detailed in the descriptor onto the platform, saving the unique identifier (ID) to later deploy it using the received ID in the deployment request. Conversely, in the second approach, the onboarding occurs when the instantiation request is received. For time-sensitive scenarios, the first approach offers a shorter deployment time because the application has already been onboarded. In contrast, for systems with memory constraints, the second approach consumes memory only when deployment is requested, even though it takes longer.

Fig. 2 illustrates the process that occurs when a MEC application experiences a malfunction (e.g., the allocating node can no longer fulfill its operational criteria), and the orchestrator is alerted, indicating the need for migration. Initially, the application is attempted to be migrated within the same MEC system. If there are no available resources for redeployment within the MEC system, the MEO sends a message via the federation interface, specifying the migration requirement along with the necessary resources. Upon receiving a migration request, each federated MEO extracts the specified requirements, collects status information from every MEC host within its system, and employs Algorithm 1 to determine the feasibility of accommodating the incoming request. Among the MEOs that respond with the ability to allocate the application within a specified time window, the one closest to the origin

Fig. 2. MEC application internal and external migration workflow.

system is selected. Once a destination system is selected, the origin MEO transmits the descriptor file of the application through the MEO-to-MEO interface, and the destination MEO begins the onboarding process. Subsequently, the destination node is forwarded to the MECPCM, which then interacts with the VIM to initiate the deployment process. The original MEC application remains operational and intact until the destination instantiation is successfully established and operational. The origin MEO receives a confirmation message confirming the successful migration, allowing it to proceed with the deletion process of the original MEC application.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section reviews the testing methodology and performance evaluation, emphasizing deployment and cross-MEC-system migration times, along with orchestrator resource utilization in SA and NSA modes. Additionally, system performance is assessed in scenarios both with and without the MEO, especially when handling high volumes of simultaneous requests, referencing Kubernetes' (K8s) default scheduling [20] as the baseline for comparison.

A. Testing Methodology

The experimental setup consists of three MEC systems deployed on a physical testbed, each one comprising a four-node K8s cluster. The MEC hosts are constructed using a combination of Intel NUC 9 Pro - NUC9VXQNX units and Latitude 5410 DELL laptops, thus introducing hardware heterogeneity among the various MEC systems to enhance the resemblance to a real environment. LightEdge [21] is used as

the MECPM, and it is integrated via the southbound API of the MEO. LightEdge operates as a microservice-based module that registers and oversees active microservices, ensuring their accessibility across the platform. For each evaluation scenario, every experiment was conducted a thousand iterations and a 95% confidence interval was calculated to ensure the statistical relevance of results.

Scenario 1 aims to showcase the SA MEO’s effectiveness and reliability in deploying applications when multiple instantiation requests occur simultaneously. After initializing the MEO, a metrics exporter is set up on each node within the system. The process commences with the activation of a wall time measurement tool at the MEO upon receiving an onboarding or deployment request. Following this, the MEO internally assesses the target node status for application deployment viability. It then communicates with the MECPM and the VIM for resource allocation and the application instantiation. All these steps are performed automatically.

Scenario 2 is designed to evaluate the application migration process using the MEO-to-MEO interface in the NSA MEO mode, managing simultaneous migration requests across three distinct MEC systems. The migration process commences either when the OSS initiates a migration request directly, or when the internal logic of the NSA MEO determines that the node hosting a given application no longer meets the application’s resource requirements. This triggers the migration request and initiates the wall time measurement tool. Communication between the originating and destination MEOs is facilitated through the MEO-to-MEO interface. Once the new application is deployed, the destination MEO notifies the originating MEO, deleting the original application. All these steps are performed automatically.

B. Results Discussion

Fig. 3a displays the average time required by the various stages in the deployment process when instantiating one to fifteen applications in one MEC system (*Scenario 1*). Using Algorithm 1, the MEO selects the most suitable MEC host for deployment among those fitting the requirements. Notice that most of the delay is introduced by the initialization of the MEC applications in K8s. However, the time taken by the MEO’s operations does not exceed 0.25 s, even for the highest number of applications. Conversely, Fig. 3b shows the migration time across three MEC systems from one to fifteen MEC applications. As in the previous scenario, most of the delay is introduced by initializing the MEC applications in K8s. The time taken by the MEO-to-MEO interface and the MEO’s Algorithm 1 operations remains below 0.65 s, even when handling the highest number of simultaneous migration requests (*Scenario 2*).

Fig. 4 showcases the resource utilization of the MEO during the instantiation and migration tasks. In Fig. 4a, both scenarios exhibit a linear increase in CPU consumption as the number of simultaneous requests rises, reaching a consumption of 0.3 CPUs when the load of requests is highest. Conversely, Fig. 4b

(a) Deployment time for instantiation of simultaneous MEC apps. (b) Migration time of simultaneous MEC apps across three MEOs.

Fig. 3. Results comparison of simultaneous app instantiation and migration time with three MEC orchestrators.

Fig. 4. MEO resource consumption (CPU and RAM) in simultaneous MEC applications allocation and migration requests.

illustrates slight fluctuations in RAM consumption, maintaining an average value of approximately 90 MB.

Table II displays the deployment and migration success rates across two scenarios. Compared to the default Kubernetes scheduling mechanism, Algorithm 1 in Table II achieves higher success rates in Scenario 1, leading to more efficient computational resource usage. For a single MEC application deployment request, both the baseline Kubernetes scheduler and the MEO achieve 100% success rates. However, as the number of simultaneous requests increases, the success rates decrease can be attributed to system saturation under the strain of high volumes of simultaneous requests per second. Even if this saturation prevents operations from maintaining 100% efficacy, Algorithm 1 performs 5% better than the baseline Kubernetes scheduling mechanism. This enhancement arises due to the default Kubernetes scheduling functionality lacks the granularity needed to fulfill the specific requirements of MEC applications, such as those for latency-sensitive environments.

In *Scenario 2*, the migration process achieved a success rate exceeding 93.3%. This was due to the high volume of

simultaneous migration requests, which caused some failures in Algorithm 1’s selection of suitable nodes for migration: due to system overload, some applications were in an initializing state, not consuming resources yet, which contributed to erroneous decisions when executing Algorithm 1.

TABLE II
SUCCESS RATES FOR DEPLOYMENT AND MIGRATION

Apps	Baseline (K8s) Deployment (%)	MEO’s Deployment (%)	MEO’s Migration (%)
1	100.0 ± 0.0	100.0 ± 0.0	100.0 ± 0.0
3	98.5 ± 0.7	99.0 ± 0.6	98.0 ± 0.7
6	95.0 ± 2.7	97.5 ± 1.1	95.4 ± 1.5
10	90.7 ± 4.8	95.3 ± 1.8	93.3 ± 2.1

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a cloud-native, platform-agnostic, lightweight MEC Orchestrator (MEO) with enhancements over the ETSI MEC architecture. Namely, the support for both SA and NSA modes aids to meet diverse system isolation and security requirements. A dedicated MEO-to-MEO interface was proposed, aligning with GSMA and ETSI MEC federation standards, which supports cross-platform MANO and resource controllability, enabling federated application management and migration across various MEC systems. Moreover, the proposed design is agnostic to MECPM implementations, thus enhancing inter-system interoperability. Dedicated resource controllability add-ons enhance hardware feature retrieval and workload scheduling. Moreover, a low-complexity algorithm was proposed for the selection of MEC hosts for application deployment in distributed MEC systems. In contrast to the baseline Kubernetes scheduler, the MEO dynamically adapts to changing network conditions and user demands by triggering migrations when a given application requirements are not met. Experimental results yielded a 95% instantiation success rate and a 93.3% success migration success rate under high requests demand, demonstrating higher system efficiency and resilience compared to the baseline Kubernetes scheduler. Future works will consider energy consumption as another key system performance metric and network performance between MEC systems during migration.

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